

Book Review

Mushirul Hasan, *Roads to Freedom: Prisoners in Colonial India*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2016, x+276 pp, ISBN: 9780199458837 (Hardcover), Rs. 795/-

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ABSTRACT

Freedom movement is one of the most discussed topics of history of Independent India. Despite this, imprisonment has not been studied in much detail. Mushirul Hasan, through his book *Roads to Freedom: Prisoners in Colonial India*, has tried to bridge the gap. He shows that prisons were unique spaces where freedom fighters across the undivided India could meet and discuss with each other. He has selected some of the best patriots, namely Mohammad Ali Jauhar, Maulana Azad, Ali Sardar Jafri, Hasrat Mohani, M. N. Roy, MK Gandhi, JL Nehru, and Sarojini Naidu, to make his case. By studying their internment and the exchanges they had with each other, the book underlines a paradox: despite large-scale imprisonment, freedom movement did not slow down. Jail is theorised as a happening space where a different kind of freedom struggle was waged. Going to jail became the rite de passage for freedom fighters. Equally significant is the argument that Muslim identity, colonialism and pluralism overlapped with each other. The book highlights the role played by socialists and women in the freedom struggle. Political prisoners were not criminals as the British state portrayed them. They were idealists of the first order. This book is an ode to them.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received on

Received on

06 May 2026

Accepted on

06 June 2026

Published on

30 June 2026

KEYWORDS

Prison Studies, History of India, Colonialism, India's freedom struggle, Muslims in freedom struggle

Vol. 01, No. 01, pp. 79-84

REPRESENT URL

https://represent.co.in/index.php/rep/article/view/1.1_6

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21170850>

Mushirul Hasan's *Roads to Freedom: Prisoners in Colonial India*, published by the Oxford University Press in 2016, has an unusual subject matter. Hasan sets out for himself an onerous task of establishing that internment did not slow down nationalist struggle, rather accelerated it albeit inadvertently. Prisons, Hasan posits, were not a space devoid of vitality; they were rather a space where considerable intermingling happened and ideas were exchanged. This book is about the best of freedom fighters, who courted arrest for the love of their country. Despite being ill-treated, inmates lived with the desire to further the cause of freedom.

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The book has twelve chapters and runs into around 275 pages. Most chapters are biographical, that is, they deal with a single historical figure. The last chapter, conclusion, is on political prisoners after Independence. Hasan has clearly stated the book is meant for the younger generation to acquaint them with the sacrifices and dreams of their ancestors. Today's youth takes India's freedom for granted overlooking the fact that this has been achieved after much sacrifice. It revisits the freedom movement not merely as a chapter in history but as a source of inspiration. The book has used both Urdu and English references from the published works, prison memoirs, collected volumes, jail records, biographies and autobiographies. This way the book is also intended for specialists working on prison studies and/ or Freedom movement of India.

The book focuses on select few political prisoners participating in the freedom struggle mainly from early 1920s to late 1930s. It locates India's freedom movement within the larger anti-colonial struggle happening across the world. Jail is theorised as a happening space where a different kind of freedom struggle was waged. Going to jail became the *rite de passage* for the freedom fighters. Most of the inmates in the book were interacting with one other. Here we see the role played by Jawaharlal Nehru and Mahatma Gandhi alongside women, socialists, Muslims (and Sikhs) is highlighted.

Hasan describes the mundane life of prison in detail. Right from the trial, entry, food and clothes to friendships, debates and finally release from the jails, everything is discussed. Jail life required adjusting to a completely new way of life (p.50). Government committees, political parties and individuals suggested reforms for the jail management, but superintendents rejected these. Politically sensitive news were clipped out or inked out heavily (p.28). Most of the jail officials were cruel, and food and dress were instruments of subjugation. Untidy and ill-fitting prison uniforms were given to all the convicts while the quality of food served was poor; the mortality was far too great (p.34). Inmates regularly fell ill: Maulana Azad lost weight, and M.N. Roy got seriously ill. The Deoband scholar, Husain Ahmad Madani, was handcuffed. Iron fetters were put on Ram Manohar Lohia in Bareilly prison (p. 38) and on Muzaffar Ahmad and his associates arrested in Kanpur Conspiracy Case (1924). Kanpur case was a landmark colonial trial where the British government arrested and jailed prominent early Indian socialists, accusing them of plotting to overthrow British rule and establish a Bolshevik-inspired revolution. It was not only pain and suffering behind the stone walls. People played games, and made new friends. Motilal Nehru recited the Persian poet Hafiz Shirazi (p.138). During the Quit India commotion Kisan Mehta could see Yusuf Meherally sending basic necessities for his fellow inmates in Yervada jail (pp. 145-6). No matter what, most of the prisoners remained faithful to a humanistic conception of nationhood.

Mohammad Ali Jauhar was a poet and an appealing orator. He enjoyed goodwill of Gandhi, Jawaharlal Nehru and the *ulamas* of Deoband. In 1921 at the Khilafat Conference in Karachi, he stated 'It is in every way religiously unlawful for a Mussalman at the present moment to continue in the British army or to enter the army or to induce others to join the army' (p.73). Afterwards, the police arrested him along with his younger brother Shaukat Ali, Bharti Krishna Tirathji, Saifuddin Kitchlew, Pir Ghulam Mujadid, Maulana Nisar Ahmad, and Husain Ahmad Madani. That he enjoyed trust of vast amount of people can be gauged from the fact that he was elected President of the Congress in 1923.

Maulana Abul Kalam Azad spent over a decade of his life in British prisons: 1916-1920 in Ranchi jail, between 1930-3 in Meerut district jail for being part of Civil Disobedience and finally, 1942 to 1945 in Ahmednagar Fort for participating in the Quit India movement. Azad penned the *Tazkira* and the *Tarjuman al-Quran* while in prison, both promoting the ideals of pluralism. All-India Azad Muslim Conference was his brainchild to propagate the idea of composite nationality. Partition broke his heart. In his speech at Delhi's Red Fort after Independence he insisted again on India's rich diversity of life was India's strength for centuries. Azad's legacy lives on through his books, *India Wins Freedom* (1958) and *Ghubar-e Khatir* (1946).

The 1930s saw socialism capture the imagination of Urdu poets and other sections of the intelligentsia. Poets started to speak for the poor and the hungry. Their only enemy became poverty and colonialism. Many poets were imprisoned for writing against the British imperialism. Their poems reveal the everyday lives of prisoners. Ali Sardar Jafri was imprisoned in Lucknow's jail as a postgraduate student. Hasrat Mohani was jailed several times in his life. He found refuge in poetry during those tiring times. Hasrat held extremely radical views. He declared total freedom as his ultimate goal as early as in 1921 (p.111). For Hasrat, socialism and Islam complemented each other (p.113). It was he who coined the slogan *Inquilab Zindabad* (p.114). He was so down-to-earth that he preferred to walk even while visiting the rajas of Salempur and Mahmudabad, and the *ulamas* of Firangi Mahal (p.248). He stayed in a nearby mosque while attending the Constituent Assembly to avoid government's expense (p.248).

M. N. Roy was a communist with global connections. He was sentenced to twelve years rigorous imprisonment in 1932 for a conspiracy against the King-Emperor. Roy used his time in jail to (re)construct his ideas (pp.127-9). He agreed with Marx that historical forces are more important than great men to change the course of history. He wrote on the evils of poverty. His *The Historical Role of Islam* (1939) was written when he was serving his term in a jail.

Gandhi was sentenced several times by the government during his stay in South Africa. In India his jail terms were longer and came every time the British felt threatened. In total he spent more than five years in jail, mainly between 1922 and 1942. Visitors were denied access to meet him. Gandhi felt that India was a vast prison, and the British officials were its superintendents. Jawaharlal Nehru spent nearly nine years of his life in jail. In 1940 the government put him in Gorakhpur Jail, held the trial inside the prison, and imposed the heaviest sentence. In Ahmadnagar Fort, Nehru and Asaf Ali spent evenings discussing, what later developed into the book, *The Discovery of India* (1946). Nehru also used to write letters to Indira that developed into a book *Letters from a Father to his Daughter* (1928).

Women contributed to the freedom struggle either by participating directly or by supporting their husbands or families. Many women participated in the Civil Disobedience. Among them the names of Avantikabai Gokhale and Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay are prominent. Sarojini Naidu bore hardships during the Home Rule protests and the Rowlatt satyagraha. Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay and Mridula Sarabhai courted arrest bravely. All the women from the Nehru family faced imprisonment be it Kamla Nehru, Krishna Nehru, Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit or Indira Gandhi. Women such as the mother of Ali brothers, Begum M. A. Ansari, Atiya Fyzee and many others were all partners in freedom struggle. Rashid Jahan, trained as a doctor, raised funds for the Bengal Famine and helped women through medical care (pp.106, 133). Nishatul Nisa stood with her husband Hasrat Mohani in his fight for an independent India (pp.117-8). It requires sensitivity to understand the importance of care and affection in the rough and tumble of the anti-colonial struggle. The book under review shows that sensibility.

Apart from the aforementioned prominent nationalist faces, the book mentions a plethora of heroes and heroines. Among these, two are worth mentioning. First is Khan Abdul Ghaffar Khan who spent decades in detention. He established the principle that the concept of *ummah* did not come in conflict with Indian citizenship. Another is the key conspirator of the 'Silk Letter Conspiracy' (*Tehrik-e Reshmi Rumal*) of 1916. It was a scheme that Mahmud Hasan and his master Ubaidullah Sindhi had devised to destroy the British rule but the authorities intercepted letters written on silk cloth leading to mass arrests and exile of the prominent leaders

Hasan presents a gloomy picture while talking about the fate of the freedom fighters in newly Independent India. He laments that though some were justly honoured, many were simply ignored. Jaiprakash Narayan continued working for a socialist vision of India. Saifuddin Kitchlew secured no office. Marxist activists, writers, and poets marched on with their usual frugal lifestyle. P. C. Joshi and Kalpana Dutt stayed in a rented house in Kolkata. Muqimuddin

Faruqi lived in a small house above the party office in Delhi. Muzaffar Ahmad led a marginalized social existence. Kaifi and Shaukat Azmi remained busy working for *social* and *economic* freedom.

Through this book, Mushirul Hasan has altered the way we look at prison life and its importance in India's freedom struggle. He succeeds in showing that political prisoners in colonial India were not docile bodies accepting the penal logic of the colonial state. Their vision and ideals remained intact, though their bodies sometimes caved in. This book illuminates colonial-era prisons as spaces where debates happened, friendships were made, poetry recited and ideas exchanged. Political prisoners were not criminals as the state portrayed them. It also foregrounds the equally important roles played by socialist leaders in the freedom struggle. Further, lesser known figures appear alongside well known nationalist figures while the role of women is shown in a nuanced way.

Lived Islam in south Asia overlapped with anti-colonial struggle and composite nationalism. We can see this from the examples of Mohammad Ali, Maulana Azad, Hasrat Mohani, Bacha Khan, Husain Ahmad Madani and others. India's Muslims were fighting the British alongside their Hindu and Sikh brethren; their idea of motherland was a united India. This is one important inference I drew while reading the book and it prompted me to review the book even though it has been a decade after publication.

Freedom fighters knew well that the roads to freedom pass through jails; and they proudly took part in it despite difficult situations. Surprisingly, Nehru pointed in a BBC interview later in 1953 that it was a good thing for a person to go to prison for a short while (BBC News India, 2023).

One major shortcoming of the book though is that it has not mentioned Christian freedom fighters nor has detailed any Sikh political prisoners. Hasan is also silent on Independence movement in south India or Adivasi assertion against British India. Despite these drawbacks, the book makes its mark by humanising political prisoners and giving them voices. This is getting challenging in today's time when not only individuals but also social groups are = criminalised by the state and political parties for protesting against any excesses. This is one of the reasons I would recommend this book. Historians, journalists, lawyers, laymen or even experts trying to understand the trials and tribulations of the political prisoners of the India's National Movement will need to go through this book. This can be their roads to freedom.

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